

CASE REPORT

Case report: Open extraction of impacted supernumerary mandibular premolar

Angelyka Pama ^{ID}, Hellene Fuego ^{ID}, Klariz Ira Solmayor ^{ID},
Gilynn Luna ^{ID}, Katreena Mangco ^{ID}, Sheann Rabulan ^{ID}

ABSTRACT

A 24-year-old female patient presented to the clinic with hyperdontia on the permanent mandibular left second premolar which hinders his daily activities due to sensitivity. It was decided to proceed with a conservative surgical intervention— an open extraction, to avoid causing excessive damage to the surrounding oral structures. The prognosis was favorable with this treatment procedure because of the absence of postoperative complications and the patient remained asymptomatic during the healing process. Thorough knowledge in recognizing signs suggesting the presence of supernumerary teeth is important. This enables the clinician to formulate an accurate diagnosis and treatment plan that could minimize the side effects on permanent dentition as a part of preventive dentistry.

Keywords supernumerary teeth, supernumerary mandibular premolar, impaction, open extraction

Corresponding author

Angelyka Pama; Cebu City, Cebu;
anes.pama.swu@phinmaed.com

1 | Introduction

Supernumerary teeth (ST), also known as hyperdontia, is defined as having more teeth than normal dentition. It is believed that there are several factors for its development, such as inherited, genetic, environmental, and dental lamina-related. Factors that may also cause the development of this phenomenon are pathologic states, such as hyperactivity of dental lamina

or traumatic injuries. The treatment modality of ST is determined by multiple factors; their position, number, any possible difficulties from the surgical intervention, and their potential impact on the normal growing dentition.¹ The surgical extraction of ST is the recommended treatment procedure when the function and aesthetics have been compromised. The extraction of clinically visible teeth is a relatively quick outpatient procedure, however, teeth that are broken, below the surface, or impacted require a more

involved method which necessitates surgical access and tooth resectioning for complete removal. Hence, this procedure should be performed with precision and accuracy to prevent iatrogenic injury for a better prognosis and improved postoperative healing.²

This case report aimed to give insight into the surgical approach used in the extraction of an impacted supernumerary mandibular premolar, to prepare clinicians which may help in assisting them in terms of decision-making of such cases most efficiently and conservatively— therefore providing quality service for patient satisfaction.

2 | Case presentation section

2.1 Chief complaint

A 24-year-old female patient presented to the dental clinic with the chief complaint, “I feel sensitivity every so often. I do not know if it is because of my mandibular left premolar which is mobile or because of my composite first molar. I desire for it to be removed to be certain.”

2.2 Medical history

The patient is a relatively healthy adult with no relevant medical findings. However, he claimed to have an allergy to Amoxicillin.

2.3 Dental history

The patient had undergone a routine dental exam approximately 4 years prior during which two impacted supernumerary premolars were detected on each side of his lower arch. In the same year, the impacted right supernumerary premolar was removed by his previous dentist through a surgical extraction. Multiple composite restorations were recorded on the patient’s mandibular arch, specifically tooth #36, #37, #46, and #47. The patient has also received an orthodontic treatment for the alignment of his maxillary teeth (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Intraoral photographs of the patient. (A) Maxilla (B) Mandible (C) Labial (D) Left (E) Right

2.3 Diagnosis

Upon taking a radiographic examination, a radiopacity was

Figure 2. Panoramic radiograph revealing the impacted supernumerary tooth on the lower left quadrant.

identified as a supernumerary mandibular premolar embedded within the mandibular ridge, located inferior and lingual to tooth #35 (Figure 2).

2.4 Prognosis

The extraction of the supernumerary mandibular left premolar has a good prognosis due to the absence of postoperative complications and the patient remained asymptomatic throughout the healing process.

2.5 Treatment

The patient undertook an open tooth extraction of his impacted mandibular left ST using a simple envelope flap incision technique. The patient was under anesthesia through inferior alveolar and lingual nerve blocks with multiple local infiltrations. A prescription of antibiotics was given for 7 days (500mg Clindamycin to be taken 1 capsule every 8 hours 3 days before surgery and the remaining 4 antibiotics were taken post-operation). About 30 minutes before surgery,

Figure 3. CBCT scan depicting the anatomical morphology and orientation of the impacted ST.

500mg Mefenamic Acid was given, and 200mg Celecoxib was taken in 1 capsule every 12 hours for 5 days.

3 | Discussion

ST is any dentition that exceeds the normal pattern of deciduous and permanent teeth.³ In the diagnosis of ST, a radiographic examination in addition to a clinical assessment should be performed for reliability especially if aberrant clinical signs are discovered.⁴ In addition, the use of a cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) scan is recommended, it offers 3D information on the morphologies and placements of teeth with a volumetric assessment of the pulp/tooth ratio.⁵ According to Rajab and Hamdan⁶, and Liu et al⁷, supernumerary teeth are typically properly oriented. However, in this case, an inverted ST was detected on the lingual side of tooth #35 after conducting a CBCT examination (Figure 3).

ST affects the teeth and often generates eruption difficulties but the patient displayed no symptoms or pathologic changes. Prompt surgical removal was recommended as the standard treatment unless unjustifiably harmful to the adjacent structures. According to the radiographs, there was minimal risk of iatrogenic harm to nearby permanent dentition since root growth of tooth #35 is complete. The surgical process

was manageable; the patient was compliant and more amenable to surgical care under local anesthetic. There is no risk of neighboring root compression and absorption in the patient's ST, surveillance should be reserved for the time being. While it is vital to conduct exams regularly to assess the development of any linked complications in the future.⁸

4 | Conclusions

Impacted ST is typically detected through routine dental radiographs. There are copious methods in the management of this anomaly which could range from tooth observation or surgical intervention depending on multiple factors. Though if left in the alveolar process, the asymptomatic supernumerary premolar may cause root resorption and necrosis of the adjacent teeth, and their follicles may even develop dentigerous cysts. Hence, surgical extraction of the ST is highly recommended to avoid further complications in the permanent dentition of the patient.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank Dr. Mary Megan D. Galacio and Dr. Jonas U. Gelbolingo for providing invaluable resources and guidance throughout

the process of case completion and Southwestern University PHINMA School of Dentistry for their support in this study.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Mallya S, Lam E. *White And Pharaoh's Oral Radiology*. St. Louis (Missouri): Elsevier; 2019.
2. Zhu F, Hou D, Zhou C et al. Precise extraction of impacted supernumerary tooth in the maxillary anterior region with a digital guide plate. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2022;101(20):e29275. doi:10.1097/md.00000000000029275
3. Subasioglu A, Savas S, Kucukyilmaz E, Kesim S, Yagci A, Dundar M. Genetic background of supernumerary teeth. *Eur J Dent*. 2015;09(01):153-158. doi:10.4103/1305-7456.149670
4. Parolia A, Dahal M, Thomas M, Kundabala M, Mohan M. Management of supernumerary teeth. *Journal of Conservative Dentistry*. 2011;14(3):221. doi:10.4103/0972-0707.85791
5. Asif M, Nambiar P, Mani S, Ibrahim N, Khan I, Sukumaran P. Dental age estimation employing CBCT scans enhanced with Mimics software: Comparison of two different approaches using pulp/tooth volumetric analysis. *J Forensic Leg Med*. 2018;54:53-61. doi:10.1016/j.jflm.2017.12.010
6. Rajab L, Hamdan M. Supernumerary teeth: review of the literature and a survey of 152 cases. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2002;12(4):244-254. doi:10.1046/j.1365-263x.2002.00366.x
7. Liu D, Zhang W, Zhang Z, Wu Y, Ma X. Three-dimensional evaluations of supernumerary teeth using cone-beam

computed tomography for 487 cases. Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology, Oral Radiology, and Endodontology. 2007;103(3):403-411.
doi:10.1016/j.tripleo.2006.03.026

8. Namdev R, Bakshi L, Kumar A, Dutta S. Supernumerary teeth: Report of four unusual cases. *Contemp Clin Dent*. 2012;3(5):71.
doi:10.4103/0976-237x.95110

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

©The Author(s) 2022